
The Presentation of Speaking Materials in English Textbook for High School Level

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the performance of speaking material in the textbook "English for Senior High School 12th Class Curriculum 2013 Revised 2018" based on the criteria of an excellent textbook proposed by Savignon (2008) to illustrate the relevance of speaking material in the book. This textbook was published by the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia for twelfth-grade students through the 2013 curriculum and described the order of speaking material in the textbook. The writers also found that the relevance of the material spoke sufficiently with the 2013 English Language Competency Standards. However, some competencies did not follow the competency. The reason was that the textbook did not present the material in speaking.

Keywords: *2013 Curriculum, Speaking Materials, Textbook*

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1. Background

English is an international language, and it is very dominant in all fields of communication between nations. It is undeniable that English is needed at this time, both in academic and other fields. At this time, many jobs require applicants to have good English speaking and writing skills. That is why many people need to learn English. English learning aims to build English-language abilities such as speaking, reading, writing, and listening by the learner needs. However, speaking is the most crucial skill because it is used to determine success in English acquisition.

Mastering the speaking skill is the main part of second-and foreign language acquisition. The purpose of English education is to teach school graduates with life skills in the sense that they are expected to attain the competence required to communicate effectively (Rosyidi, 2010). Therefore, the teacher has to emphasize the improvement of students' skill in communication, particularly speaking. Several factors of the teaching and learning process must be examined to achieve competence. Materials are one of them. Materials can support and enhance the students during the teaching and learning process (Brown, 1994). Furthermore, one of the material resources for teachers is a textbook.

Most goals and objectives have already been created in a set of activities depending on what students need to learn, therefore textbooks are considered to be beneficial (Cunningsworth, 1995; Ratmanida &

Suryanti, 2019). According to Ratmanida & Suryanti (2019), the textbook benefits teachers by helping them prepare materials and achieve teaching aims and objectives and student by helping them achieve their learning needs.

There are many media offered to teachers to help the process of teaching activities. Many publishers have published textbooks for various classes and levels of education. This research is intended to describe the presentation of speaking material in English textbooks for High School 12th Grade Curriculum 2013 Revision 2018 based on good textbook criteria and describe the sequence of speaking material in the textbook with a predetermined curriculum. Because the government has now changed the 2006 curriculum (KTSP) to the 2013 curriculum (K13), this means that the teacher must create a syllabus that applies to all schools in Indonesia. A good textbook should be curriculum-relevant and capable of assisting with curriculum implementation (Budiarty, 2016). As a result, the teacher needs to choose and analyze the contents of the English textbook. Therefore, in this research, we want to analyze the performance of speaking material in the textbook "English for Senior High School " based on the criteria of an excellent textbook.

2. Method

The research object is an English textbook for high school students in 12th grade published by Indonesia's Ministry of Education and Culture. The data of this study are all speaking material presented in the textbook; the materials are dialogues, information about specific events, activities, instructions, pictures, and photos. This study focused on the presentation of speaking material and analyzing the order of speaking materials with the 2013 English standard. The data of the speaking material was taken from the first and second semesters in the textbook. This study was designed to use descriptive qualitative analysis results to have a simple preferable description of a phenomenon (Lambert et al., 2012). Descriptive qualitative research is essential when researchers want to know who was involved, what was involved, and where things happened with events. Therefore, this study was in the way of analyzing documents, namely analyzing the suitability of speaking material in the textbook "English for Senior High School 12th Class Curriculum 2013 Revised 2018" with 2013 Curriculum through several aspects to determine the presence of speaking material in the textbook "English for Senior High School 12th Class Curriculum 2013 Revised 2018" and the suitability of the speaking material sequence based on the 2013 English Standard Competency.

3. Finding and Discussion

The first discussion was about the presentation of the textbook. Dealing with textbook presentations, the authors used criteria drawn from Savignon (2008). To analyze the textbook presentations, there are three criteria that researchers use. These three criteria are that the material must be attractive and use photos, pictures, graphics, and colours. In addition, the material must encourage students to look for language samples outside the book and the classroom, and the material must encourage students to use language in everyday life.

The first criterion of good speaking material is that the material must be attractive, using photos, pictures, charts, and colours. These criteria are needed to attract students to explore, ask questions, start conversations, and avoid boredom. For some of these criteria, the authors found in chapter one of dialogue one, and there is a picture that accompanies the speaking material. This picture is related to the material in the section about asking for and giving help to others. The dialogue depicts a patient who cannot go to school because of a disease. The picture shown was suitable with the delivered dialogue, which is a picture of a doctor who was examining a boy and accompanied by a female nurse. There are several more images in the following dialogues: dialogue two, three, and four. However, the pictures are no more interesting than the picture in the first dialogue. The images provided in dialogues two, three, and four only show the gender and profession of the person in dialogue.

Besides, the authors found that not all reading material in textbooks was arranged according to the criteria in the first chapter, namely with good speaking material. Based on the findings, there is a reason the author did not arrange speaking material based on the first criterion, which is to combine speaking skills with other skills, as found in chapters two, three, and four in this textbook.

The second criterion is material that should encourage students to look for language samples outside the book and the classroom. This criterion will give students examples, but also students can feel encouraged to look for sample forms or patterns of other languages as provided by textbooks in speaking material. Within these criteria, the authors found that the content could encourage students to look for language samples outside the book and the classroom. As the following picture will show, the exercise can allow students to make other new examples. The material requires students to practice first, and then they must proceed in a manner as exemplified by a different topic. With new topics, students can have a conversation based on what they have learned before. Not only that, but students can also find other expressions that have the same meaning as they have learned before.

Furthermore, the authors also found some speaking material that was not arranged based on the second criterion. This is because the textbook authors took do not provide speaking material, as found in chapters two, three, and four. However, the textbook writers still provide other question exercises for speaking material in chapters with no speaking material.

The third criterion is material that should encourage students to use language in everyday life. This criterion is helpful if the textbook presents several examples that students can use to speak the language in their daily lives. For example, seeing the picture from the additional speaking material below, students can apply dialogue with their friends, so students will know that how to use the expression of asking and giving help is like the example given. One more thing that proves the speaking material in this chapter can encourage students to use it in everyday life is that they need to make other expressions based on a predetermined topic.

Like the second criterion, the authors also found some speaking material that was not arranged based on the third criterion. Again, this is because textbook writers do not provide speaking material and are found in chapters three and four.

Second, not all speaking competencies are provided by the textbook. For example, the authors found that some speaking competencies were not presented in speaking activities but other skills. The authors also found that some speaking competencies do not have speaking activity in textbooks. In addition, the authors also found several activities that combined speaking competencies with other competencies.

The second discussion was about the order of speaking material in the textbook. In the textbook analyzed by the authors, the material presented in the textbook is per 2013 essential competencies for the twelfth grade of high school. The compatibility of basic competencies with the order of material in textbooks is that this textbook was published by the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia. This ministry regulates all matters regarding education in Indonesia, including 2013 basic competencies.

4. Conclusion

Based on those objectives, several conclusions can be drawn.

The first conclusion is that there is a reason the writer did not compile based on the first criteria. The second criterion is material that should encourage students to look for language samples from outside the book and the classroom. Based on the findings, this criterion is fulfilled by most of the speaking material found in the textbook. However, there is some speaking material that is not arranged based on the second criterion. The third criterion is material that should encourage students to use language in everyday life. This criterion is also fulfilled by most of the material spoken in textbooks. That is because the author of the textbook does not provide speaking material.

Second, the order of all speaking material in textbooks was arranged based on the competence of the English standard in 2013. Thus, the authors concluded the reason for the suitability of basic competencies with the textbook's material order; this textbook was published by the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia.

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